

HISTORIES ACROSS THE RED SEA AND THE PERSIAN GULF

REDMIX Online Seminar Series

14 January • 17:30 CET

**Slavery, Manumission, and Social Change
in the Persian Gulf (19th - 20th Centuries)**

Jerzy Zdanowski (Andrzej Frycz Modrzewski Kraków University)

28 January • 17:30 CET

**Imperial Iran in the Red Sea:
From the Suez Crisis to the Ethiopian Revolution**

Robert Steele (Institute of Iranian Studies, Austrian Academy of Sciences)

29 January • 17:00 CET

The Color Black: Enslavement and Erasure in Iran

Beeta Baghoolizadeh (Middle East Institute, Columbia University)

Organized & moderated by **Sara Zanotta** (University of Turin)

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